

Synthesis of tetraaza macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes; antibacterial and catalytic studies

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Manuscript received 25 January 2008, revised 11 September 2008, accepted 16 September 2008

Abstract : A series of new Schiff base Pd^{II} complexes of the type [Pd(L)]X₂ [where, L = HBOADO, TBACD, OBACD, HBOADT, DBACDT, TBAHD and X = Cl⁻] have been synthesized by non-template method. The complexes were characterized with the help of elemental analyses, conductance measurements, magnetic measurements, infrared, NMR (¹H, ¹³C), mass, electronic spectral studies and thermal analysis. Based on the spectral data, square-planar geometry is tentatively proposed to all the complexes. The biological activities of these complexes have been tested *in vitro* to evaluate their activity against Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria and were found to be more active than streptomycin and ampicillin. [Pd(HBOADO)]Cl₂ and [Pd(OBACD)]Cl₂ complexes were studied on the catalytic reduction reactions of 2-nitroanisole, 3-nitroanisole, 4-nitroanisole, 2-nitrobenzoic acid, 3-nitrobenzoic acid, 4-nitrobenzoic acid under mild conditions. The reduced products were treated with nitrous acid followed by β-naphthol and the developed colored products were determined spectrophotometrically. [Pd(HBOADO)]Cl₂ is found to be more efficient than [Pd(OBACD)]Cl₂.

Keywords : Synthesis, macrocyclic, palladium(II), antibacterial, catalytic studies.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of Schiff base metal complexes involving nitrogen donor ligands has excited great interest among chemists in recent years due to their applications in catalysis and their relevance to bioinorganic systems. A good number of research papers have been published on the synthesis and characterization of macrocyclic Schiff base complexes indicating that this is an active field of study¹⁻⁶. In past decades there has been considerable interest in the synthesis and catalytic properties of Pd^{II} Schiff base complexes^{7,8}. Further these catalysts have attracted considerable attention in industry due to the generation of inexpensive products. The current interest is often inspired by some other applications and importance in the development of bioinorganic area^{9,10}. Literature survey reveals that most of the existing orthophthalaldehyde (OPA) based macrocyclic metal compounds were synthesized by template method involving the direct treatment of OPA with diamine in the presence of metal salts¹¹⁻¹⁴. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are no reports on the synthesis of macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds derived from *o*-phthalaldehyde. In view of these interesting aspects, we have synthesized and

characterized the Pd^{II} macrocyclic Schiff base complexes. The present paper deals with the striking structural features, synthesis, catalysis and biological applications of these complexes.

Results and discussion

In the present investigations, six new macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes were synthesized by treating PdCl₂ with six N₄ donor macrocyclic ligands separately. These complexes are crystalline yellow solids, non-hygroscopic, freely soluble in methanol and stable up to 209 °C. The percentages of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined experimentally using CHN analyzer. The percentage of palladium in macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes was determined by gravimetric procedure using dimethylglyoxime as precipitating agent. The molar conductance values for all the macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds (10⁻³ M) were determined in dimethylformamide. These values were found between 53 and 60 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating 1 : 2 electrolytic nature. The electrolytic nature of these compounds is due to the presence of two chloride ions outside the coordination sphere¹⁵. The presence of chloride ions in these compounds was detected by the addition of silver nitrate.

Table 1. Physical, analytical and electronic spectral data of macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes

Compd.	Pd ^{II} compd./ molecular formula	ΔM ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	λ_{max} (nm)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
				C	H	N	Pd
1	[Pd(HBOADO)]Cl ₂ C ₁₉ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₂ Pd	53.0	470, 280	40.05 (39.91)	3.76 (3.89)	19.77 (19.60)	18.44 (18.61)
2	[Pd(TBACD)]Cl ₂ C ₁₈ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₂ Pd	54.5	474, 288	41.11 (40.97)	3.33 (3.44)	16.02 (15.93)	20.06 (20.16)
3	[Pd(OBACD)]Cl ₂ C ₁₄ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ Pd	56.2	465, 285	39.96 (39.88)	4.64 (4.78)	13.33 (13.29)	25.46 (25.23)
4	[Pd(HBOADT)]Cl ₂ C ₁₉ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₈ S ₂ Pd	60.0	480, 290	37.55 (37.79)	3.79 (3.67)	18.42 (18.56)	17.77 (17.62)
5	[Pd(DBACDT)]Cl ₂ C ₁₈ H ₁₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ S ₂ Pd	58.0	478, 300	40.81 (40.81)	2.96 (3.04)	10.66 (10.58)	19.98 (20.08)
6	[Pd(TBAHD)]Cl ₂ C ₁₈ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₆ S ₂ Pd	59.5	472, 310	38.76 (38.62)	3.05 (3.24)	14.96 (15.01)	19.11 (19.01)

The magnetic susceptibility measurements have been carried out for macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds and these compounds were found to be diamagnetic and hence Pd^{II} ion is in low spin configuration. The physical and analytical data (Table 1) for the newly synthesized macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes is in good agreement with the proposed molecular formulae viz. [Pd(L)]X₂.

Table 2. Infrared spectral data of macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes

Compd.	Pd ^{II} compd.	Selected IR bands (cm ⁻¹)		
		$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{Pd-N}}$
1	[Pd(HBOADO)]Cl ₂	1582	3312	504
2	[Pd(TBACD)]Cl ₂	1586	3320	512
3	[Pd(OBACD)]Cl ₂	1592	3314	515
4	[Pd(HBOADT)]Cl ₂	1598	3335	515
5	[Pd(DBACDT)]Cl ₂	1605	-	516
6	[Pd(TBAHD)]Cl ₂	1586	3378	530

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)]Cl₂.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)]Cl₂.

In the IR spectra of macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes, a medium intensity band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ was shifted towards lower side about 20–26 cm⁻¹ compared to ligand spectra and appeared in the range of 1625–1600 cm⁻¹. This

supports the fact that the ligands coordinate to the metal ions through the nitrogen of C=N group in all the complexes¹⁶. This fact is further supported by the appearance of a band in the region of 530–504 cm⁻¹

Table 3. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data of macrocyclic chloro complexes of palladium(II)

Compd.	Pd ^{II} compd.	¹ H NMR peak position (δ ppm)	¹³ C NMR peak position (δ ppm)
1	[Pd(HBOADO)]Cl ₂	5.93 (4H, s, NH), 7.02–8.05 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.35 (4H, s, CH=N)	131.4, 132.6, 135.5 (12C, Ar-C), 153.6 (4C, CH=N), 173.0 (2C, C=O)
2	[Pd(TBACD)]Cl ₂	5.86 (2H, s, NH), 7.20–7.90 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.51 (4H, s, CH=N)	133.2, 134.0, 135.1, 136.9 (12C, Ar-C), 149.4, 165.4 (4C, CH=N), 156.2 (2C, C=O)
3	[Pd(OBACD)]Cl ₂	2.21–2.42 (4H, m, -CH ₂), 2.82 (4H, s, -CH ₂), 3.39–3.72 (4H, m, -CH ₂), 7.01–7.82 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.31 (2H, s, CH=N), 6.03 (2H, s, NH)	45.0, 48.0, 60.1 (6C, CH ₂), 131.4, 135.6, 136.2 (6C, Ar-C), 158.2 (2C, CH=N)
4	[Pd(HBOADT)]Cl ₂	5.84 (4H, s, NH), 7.32–7.72 (8H, dd, Ar-H), 8.32 (4H, s, CH=N)	132.0, 133.5, 138.8 (12C, Ar-C), 156.1 (4C, CH=N), 174.7 (2C, C=S)
5	[Pd(DBACDT)]Cl ₂	7.10–8.02 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.50 (4H, s, CH=N)	134.5, 135.8, 137.4, 139.1 (12C, Ar-C), 158.4 (4C, CH=N), 193.2 (2C, C=S)
6	[Pd(TBAHD)]Cl ₂	5.83 (2H, s, NH), 7.18–7.89 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.23 (4H, s, CH=N)	132.6, 134.4, 135.7, 135.8, 136.6, 138.4 (12C, Ar-C), 148.6, 163.4 (4C, CH=N), 176.0 (2C, C=S)

Fig. 3. ¹³C NMR spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)Cl₂]

assignable to ν_{M-N} vibration¹⁴. However, in the complex-3 ν_{NH} band was observed at 3314 cm⁻¹. This band was shifted towards lower side about 27 cm⁻¹ compared to the ligand spectrum indicating the coordination to the metal through nitrogen of NH group¹⁷. The characteristic bands due to the $\nu_{C=O}/\nu_{C=S}$ in the spectra of respective macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds were remain almost

unshifted¹⁸. All the characteristic bands due to the aromatic rings were also present in the expected regions¹² in all the macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds (Table 2). The IR spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)]Cl₂ (complex-4) is presented in Fig. 1.

In the ¹H NMR spectra of the macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds the integral intensities of each signal were found to agree with the number of different types of protons

Fig. 4. Mass spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)Cl₂]

Scheme 1. Structures of some macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes.

present. In all the ligands, signals were appeared in the range of δ 8.10–8.43 due to CH=N protons. However, in the spectra of macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds, these signals were observed in the up field regions of δ 8.23–8.51 confirming the coordination of nitrogen atom of this group to Pd^{II} ion¹⁹. In the spectrum of the complex-3 a broad signal was observed at δ 6.03 due to NH proton, which was shifted from δ 5.60 of ligand indicating the coordination of NH group²⁰. There is no appreciable change in the peak positions corresponding to aromatic protons¹². The ¹H NMR spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)]Cl₂ (complex-4) is presented in Fig. 2.

¹³C NMR signals for the macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds are assigned by the comparison with the spectra of corresponding macrocyclic ligands and the chemical shifts in ¹³C NMR spectra revealed a consistent pattern. In the spectra of Pd^{II} complexes, a down field shift of CH=N group was observed in the range of δ 148.6–165.4, indicate that all the ligands coordinate through the nitrogen atoms²¹. Appreciable changes in peak positions were not observed with respect to aryl carbons and carbons adjacent to oxygen/sulphur atom¹². The ¹H and ¹³C NMR data of macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes is given in Table 3. The ¹³C

NMR spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)]Cl₂ (complex-4) is presented in Fig. 3.

The macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds contain molecular ion peaks at *m/z* (M⁺) 571 (for complex-1), 527 (for complex-2), 421 (for complex-3), 603 (for complex-4), 529 (for complex-5) and 559 (for complex-6) and these values are in good agreement with the respective molecular weights of the macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds, which were calculated on the basis proposed molecular formulae. The mass spectrum of [Pd(HBOADT)]Cl₂ (complex-4) is presented in Fig. 4.

The electronic spectra of the Pd^{II} complexes were recorded in DMF. The absorption bands and their assignments are given in Table 3. Theoretically three ligand field bands are expected for square planar Pd^{II} complexes in the regions of 690–600, 555–450 and 410–370 nm, but all these three are not observed in most of the complexes. The Pd^{II} complexes prepared have been found to show a broad *d-d* transition band in the region of 480–465 nm assignable to ¹B_{1g} ← ¹A_{1g} transition typical for the square planar geometry^{22,23}. Further a relatively strong charge transfer band has been observed in the spectra of all the Pd^{II} complexes in the range of 310–280 nm.

Table 4. Minimum inhibitory concentrations of the Pd^{II} complexes and existing antibiotics

Sl. no.	Pd ^{II} compd.	Range of concentration (0.25–10 µg/ml)			
		MTCC-619	MTCC-96	MTCC-722	MTCC-109
1.	Streptomycin	2	–	–	–
2.	Ampicillin	–	–	–	–
3.	Rifampicin	5	0.25	0.25	0.25
4.	[Pd(HBOADT)]Cl ₂	7	4	3	2
5.	[Pd(DBACDT)]Cl ₂	8	5	3	3
6.	[Pd(TBAHD)]Cl ₂	10	4	2	4

The thermal analysis data of Pd^{II} complexes indicates that they are stable up to 209 °C and hence exist in anhydrous state. The DTA curves show no endothermic peaks up to 209 °C confirming the absence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes^{24–26}. The sharp decomposition corresponding to the loss of organic moiety in complexes can be seen in the DTA curves which contained one sharp exothermic peak falling in the range of 210–245 °C. The final product of decomposition of all the complexes above 680 °C corresponds to metal oxide. Considering the loss of organic moiety, the thermal stability of the palladium(II) complexes can be represented with respect to ligands as HBOADT > HBOADO > TBAHD > DBACDT > TBACD > OBACD. Though, it is difficult every time to explain the order of thermal stability in terms of the structure and the nature of the ligand, this order can be explained to some extent, on the basis of the steric factors such as bulkiness of the groups attached to the ligating groups, labile nature of ligand bonds and the number of chelate rings formed by each ligand^{27–29}.

From the electronic spectral data and the diamagnetic behavior of the complexes square planar geometry has been proposed to all the Pd^{II} complexes (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

Antimicrobial activities of macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes were studied along with metal free ligands and three existing antibacterial drugs viz. streptomycin, ampicillin and rifampicin. Preliminary screening for all the complexes was performed at fixed concentrations of 1000 µg/ml. Based on the obtained values of relative zone inhibition³⁰ only three ligands HBOACTD, DBACDT, TBAHD and their complexes viz. 4, 5 and 6 were found to be very effective. The macrocyclic Pd^{II} complexes showed more increased activity than the corresponding ligands. In addition, the above three complexes were found to be effective at different dilutions based on the activity. The minimum inhibitory concentration³¹ of these three complexes was also verified by the liquid dilution method in which the effectiveness was observed at lower concentrations. The activity of these three complexes against Gram +ve and Gram -ve bacteria were compared with the activity of existing antibacterial drugs like streptomycin, ampicillin and rifampicin and these complexes were found to be very active than streptomycin, ampicillin (Table 4). The antimicrobial activity of macrocyclic ligands and their

Pd^{II} complexes is due to the presence of C=N group (Schiff base), which were obtained by the condensation of *o*-phthalaldehyde with diamines. Especially, three ligands HBOACTD, DBACDT, TBAHD and their complexes viz. 4, 5 and 6 are more active may be due to the presence of thio group in corresponding macrocyclic ligands and their complexes (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Zones of inhibitions of macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds against four different bacteria

Optimization of catalytic process :

In the literature the reduction of nitro group was carried out on substituted aromatic nitro compounds viz. chloronitrobenzenes. In these compounds, the reduction was carried by using Au/ZrO₂. The reduction process took 1–5 h and the yield was about 90–99%. In the present investigations, the reduction of aromatic nitro compounds was carried out using hydrogen gas in the presence of macrocyclic Pd complexes and the percent yields of amino derivatives were determined spectrophotometrically by diazocoupling reaction (Table 5). In the reduction process, three molecules of hydrogen react with aromatic nitro compounds in the presence of palladium catalysts leading to amino derivatives with the elimination of two water molecules. Interestingly, the reduction was completed with in 20 min and produced about 70–90%. To compare the reduction process two types of substituted nitro compounds were selected for the reduction studies, in the first three substrates the substitution is -OCH₃ group which is an electron releasing group (*o*, *p*-directing group), whereas in the last three substrates -COOH group which is electron withdrawing group (*m*-directing group). Palladium(II) catalysts ([Pd(HBOADO)]Cl₂ and [Pd(OBACD)]Cl₂) reduced the *p*-nitroanisole at much faster rates than the corresponding *o*-nitroanisole and *m*-nitroanisole. The reduction of substituted nitroanisoles is

Table 5. Catalytic hydrogenation of Pd^{II} compounds and % yields of reduced products

Substrate	Reaction time (min)	Products	Yield (%)	
			[Pd(HBOADO)]Cl ₂	[Pd(OBACD)]Cl ₂
<i>o</i> -Nitroanisole	16	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	87	80
<i>m</i> -Nitroanisole	20	<i>m</i> -Anisidine	78	72
<i>p</i> -Nitroanisole	15	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	90	84
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	17	<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	85	78
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	12	<i>m</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	89	83
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	19	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	78	72

in the order : *p*-nitroanisole > *o*-nitroanisole > *m*-nitroanisole. It may be due to the presence of an electron releasing group on the aromatic ring. Similarly the reduction of *o/m/p*-nitrobenzoic acids is in the order : *m*-nitrobenzoic acid > *o*-nitrobenzoic acid > *p*-nitrobenzoic acid. It is due to the presence of an electronic withdrawing group on the benzene ring. However, [Pd(HBOADO)]Cl₂ is found to be more efficient when compared to [Pd(OBACD)]Cl₂ on the reduction of various organic substrates. The more efficiency of [Pd(HBOADO)]Cl₂ may be due to the symmetric structure of macrocyclic ligand which provides the metal-ligand π -electron delocalization. The formed amino derivatives (*o*-anisidine/*m*-anisidine/*p*-anisidine/2-aminobenzoic acid/3-aminobenzoic acid/4-aminobenzoic acid) were treated with nitrous acid. The diazotized products were then treated with β -naphthol³² along with other color reagents viz. 1,2-naphthaquinone-4-sulfonate³³, *p*-benzoquinone³⁴ and trisodium pentacyanoaminoferrate³⁵. Since, β -naphthol produces high molar absorptivity value than the other reagents, it was preferred for the color development. The factors affecting color development was also investigated. It was found that, two ml each of conc. hydrochloric acid and 0.1 M sodium nitrite solutions and 3 ml of 0.1 M β -naphthol solution were necessary to achieve maximum color intensity. The excess of sodium nitrite was removed by the addition of one ml of sulfamic acid solution. Addition of an excess of sulfamic acid has no effect on the color intensity of the product formed. λ_{\max} values of all the colored products were found to be around 520 nm. The color products were stable up to one hour. After one hour, the colored products were slowly degraded. The rate of degradation was 1%/min in terms of percent yields of reduction products.

Product analysis :

The infrared spectra of nitro derivatives show a broad

peak around 1358 cm⁻¹ due to the stretching of nitro group. The appearance of strong absorption band around 3300 cm⁻¹ in amino compounds indicates the N-H stretching of aromatic primary amino group. Similarly, the disappearance of broad peak 1360 cm⁻¹ indicates the reduction of nitro group into amino group. This is further confirmed by NMR spectral analysis. The NMR spectra of hydrogenated products show one additional broad peak at δ 9.20 confirming the presence of aromatic primary amino groups in them. The red colored azo dyes are formed with amino compounds by the diazotization with nitrous acid and coupling with β -naphthol³².

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and were procured from Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. All solvents used were of spectroscopic grade. Six macrocyclic ligands viz. 7,8,9,18,19,20-hexahydrodibenzo[*g,p*][1,2,4,5,10,11,13,14]octaazacyclooctadecine-8,19-dione [HBOADO], 7,8,17,18-tetrahydrodibenzo[*f,n*][1,2,4,9,11,12]-hexaazacyclohexadecine-8,17-dione [TBACD], 3, 4, 5, 6, 7,8,9,10-octahydro-2,5,8,11-benzotetraazacyclotetradecine [OBACD], 7,8,9,18,19,20-hexahydrodibenzo[*g,p*][1,2,4,5,10,11,13,14]octaazacyclooctadecine-8,19-dithione [HBOADT], 7,16-dihydrodibenzo[*e,l*][1,3,8,10]tetraazacyclotetradecine-7,16-dithione [DBACDT] and 7,8,17,18-tetrahydrodibenzo[*f,n*][1,2,4,9,11,12]hexaazacyclohexadecine-8,17-dithione [TBAHD] were prepared and characterized³. Organisms like *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC-619), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC-96), *Escherichia coli* (MTCC-722) and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (MTCC-109) from IMTECH, Chandigarh were used for antimicrobial studies. Elemental data was obtained by using a Perkin-Elmer 240C CHN elemental analyzer. UV-Vis spectra were recorded on Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, IR spectra in KBR pellets on Perkin-

Elmer-283 spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra on WH 300 (200 MHz) using $\text{CDCl}_3/\text{DMSO}$ solvent and ^{13}C NMR spectra on Varian Gemini (200 MHz) were recorded. LC-ESI MS was used to obtain mass spectra. The mixture of methanol and trifluoro acetic acid (TFA) was used to record MS. The purity of all the complexes was checked by LC-ESI MS and was in the range of 98.1–99.6%.

Synthesis of macrocyclic Pd^{II} Schiff base compounds :

A methanolic solution (20 mL) of ligand (L) was mixed to the PdCl_2 solution (20 mL, 1 : 1 0.1 M HCl, methanol) in equimolar ratio, with constant stirring and continued for about 1-1½ h. The resulting solution was concentrated under reduced pressure and a few ml of diethylether was added to initiate the crystallization. The precipitate formed was separated by suction filtration, washed with diethylether, vacuum dried to get a crystalline compound and was recrystallized using dichloromethane and diethylether solvent mixture (yield 70–78%).

Antimicrobial testing by agar diffusion : Antimicrobial testing was done by cup plate method³⁶. Sterile Petri dishes were taken to which 27 ml of molten agar is added and allowed to solidify and set for 1 h. Then 50 ml of the 24 h culture of a test organism was taken on to the agar plate and spread evenly with the sterile cotton swab. Six mm wide bores were made on the agar using a borer. The solutions of the macrocyclic metal compounds were added in to each of the bores in appropriately using a sterile tip with micropipette and labeled as Petri dishes. A similar plate was prepared by replacing macrocycle by Streptomycin sulphate. This was taken as a standard against bacteria. These dishes were then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The inhibition zone formed by the compounds against the particular test bacterial strain determined the antibacterial activities of the Pd^{II} compounds. The mean value obtained for three individual replicates was used to calculate the zone of growth inhibition of each sample. The activities of compounds were interpreted either active or inactive. The minimum inhibitory concentration required was also found when a series of dilutions were tested.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) : The minimum inhibitory concentration was determined by liquid dilution method³⁷. Stock solutions of Pd^{II} complexes with 2.5 µg/ml, 5 µg/ml, 10 µg/ml, 20 µg/ml, 50 µg/ml and 100 µg/ml concentrations were prepared with aqueous methanol solvent. The solutions of standard

drugs like Streptomycin, Ampicillin and Rifampicin were also prepared in the same concentrations. Inoculum of the overnight culture was prepared. In a series of tubes 1 ml each of macrocyclic Pd^{II} complex solution with different concentrations were taken and 0.2 ml of the inoculum was added to each tube. Further 3.8 ml of the sterile water was added to each of the test tubes. These test tubes were incubated for 24 h and observed for the presence of turbidity. The absorbance of the suspension of the inoculum was observed with spectrophotometer at 555 nm. This method was repeated by replacing Pd^{II} complexes with drugs like Streptomycin, Ampicillin and Rifampicin for comparison.

Catalytic reduction : The DMF-water mixture is saturated with hydrogen and then a 0.01 mmol of catalyst $[\text{Pd}(\text{HBOADO})]\text{Cl}_2$ (complex-1) was added. The catalyst goes in to the solution in few min. The reaction system was evacuated and flushed with hydrogen for few min and a 0.01 mmol of 2-nitroanisole/3-nitroanisole/4-nitroanisole/2-nitrobenzoicacid/3-nitrobenzoicacid/4-nitrobenzoicacid in DMF was injected. The hydrogen absorption begins as soon as the shaking is started. The process was continued for 1 h. The resulting mixture was cooled and extracted with chloroform, the organic layer was separated, washed with water and dried over magnesium sulphate to give the *o*-anisidine/*m*-anisidine/*p*-anisidine/2-aminobenzoicacid/3-aminobenzoicacid/4-aminobenzoicacid. The amino derivatives formed were treated with two ml each of conc. hydrochloric acid and 0.1 M sodium nitrite solutions followed by three ml of 0.1 M β-naphthol solution and the total solution was made upto 10 ml double distilled water. The colored products formed were determined spectrophotometrically at 520 nm from the respective calibration curves derived from the standard solutions of above amino derivatives. The procedure is repeated by taking the other catalyst.

Conclusions :

Six macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds were synthesized by treating palladium(II) chloride with six macrocyclic ligands separately. By the elemental and spectral analysis, square-planar geometry has been assigned to these complexes. Since, two chloride ions are present outside the coordination sphere, these compounds have electrolytic nature. The macrocyclic Pd^{II} compounds were found to have significant antibacterial activity. Out of six, three

complexes were found to be very active than the streptomycin and ampicillin due to the presence of this group in corresponding macrocyclic ligands. [Pd(HBOADO)]Cl₂ and [Pd(OBACD)]Cl₂ complexes were studied on the catalytic reduction reactions of 2-nitroanisole, 3-nitroanisole, 4-nitroanisole, 2-nitrobenzoic acid, 3-nitrobenzoic acid, 4-nitrobenzoic acid under mild conditions and [Pd(HBOADO)]Cl₂ is found to be more efficient than [Pd(OBACD)]Cl₂.

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